

STATISTICAL TOOLS FOR RESEARCH ANALYSIS: USAGE AND INTERPRETATION

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Abstract

Lecturers in our tertiary institutions need to use statistical packages to analyze data. By so doing, they will be able to supervise their research students better and also assess the analysis of data done by research students more efficiently and effectively. In this world of globalization, it is desirable for every individual to be computer literate in order to function effectively well in the society. The use of statistical tools enhances the ability to get quick results when data has been collected in research work.

The statistical packages for social sciences (SPSS) is one of the popular packages used in analyzing research data. This paper attempts to demonstrate how these packages could be used in analyzing some selected descriptive and inferential topics in statistics.

Keywords: *Statistical tools, Research and Usage*

Introduction

Tertiary institutions worldwide, Nigeria inclusive has the three pronged responsibility of promoting sound teaching, quality research as well as contributing effectively to community development. To this end lecturers are aware of the need for them to publish and flourish through embarking on some quality research. In most cases and especially in education, empirical researches are undertaken which calls for the need to analyze the data collected.

It is becoming old styles and clumsy for one to attempt to analyze data using manual techniques. The volume and diversity of data collected when

embarking on quality publishable research calls for the need to use modern methods of analyzing data. As Adedayo (2011) observes modern world advocates the need for computer literacy for all and especially lecturers in tertiary institutions that need to use the modern tool of information and technology in their day to day activities. Lecturers who must of necessity carry out some research work need to be able to identify and use various software for analyze quantitative research data.

Many statistical packages abound that could be used in analyzing research data. These packages are available either in the relevant markets or could be downloaded free from the internet. Most of them are user friendly and can be easily utilized with the step by step instruction provided on time for their usage.

One of the popular software packages is statistical packages for social science (SPSS). It is so disheartening to note that while many lecturers can confirm their awareness of the existence of these packages only few can attest to be versatile at utilizing these packages. Some lecture often pay outsiders to analyze their data and more often than not, these outsiders may end up coming out with a wrong output and times analysis leading to faulty finding. Therefore, it is pertinent for lecturers to understand the use of these packages, when adopting at the use of these statistical software in analyzing data and interpreting the output effectively, they in turn will be able to supervise their research student more efficiently and effectively.

The Importance of Statistics in Education Research

It is a well known fact that statistics plays an important role in educational research. The principal aim of research is to bring out new facts and test new ideas in order to make contributions to knowledge. In quantitative research, the information collected are often expressed in numerical forms and analysis of such is best done using the tool of statistical

(Adedayo 2010). In research, statistics find application right from the point of data collection. Sampling techniques are very useful in determining the simple to be used for research (Adebayo 2011). Simulation of simple random numbers guide sample selection and the use of statistical software enhances this. If a questionnaire is used for the research, manual analysis of data will prove tedious especially for a large sample. The work will be greatly simplified if the necessary coding is done on the items of the questionnaire thereby making it easy to collate the responses in the questionnaires for statistical analysis (Adebayo 2011).

Generally, statistics can be classified into descriptive and inferential statistical. Descriptive statistics include classification and summarization of data using frequency count, diagrammatic and graphical representation of data, computation of measures of central tendency and measure of dispersion. Others includes linear regression, correlation, time series analysis etc. (Esan and Okafor 2004)

On the other hand, inferential statistics enables us to make differences about a population base on carefully selected representative sample. With inferential statistics one can test postulated hypotheses using parametric and non-parametric test. In inferential statistics, the Z and student t - test prove useful when carrying out test of hypothesis on differences in means of one or two samples depending on whether the population parameter is known or unknown. For two, three or more sample test, differences in means can be tested using Analysis of variance (ANOVA). In experimental research involving pre-test and post - test designs, one can use the pretest as co-variance in order to obtain a more robust result using Analysis of Co-variance (ANCOVA) and multivariate Analysis of variance (MANOVA).

The use of statistical software enables one to analyze results at a faster rate and with more accuracy. Many of the available statistical software packages are similar in output thus, little difficulty is encountered in the

interpretation of the output. Others include: EXCEL, SAS, MINITAB, STATA etc.

Using the SPSS Statistical Package to Analyze Data.

This software package is formally known as statistical packages for social sciences. It is a software useful for survey, data mining, text analysis and other simple statistical analysis. SPSS processing statistical computing packages was developed by a political science postgraduate student, Norman Nie and his colleague Hadlai Hull at Stanford University. The first version of this software was released in 1968 and since then various and improved versions have been released. There is also an on going research to bring up further versions for more advanced. Research based tools of ICT (Information Communication Technology) (Kirkpatrick and Feeney 2009). This statistical computing will simplify and speed up analysis no matter the size of the data.

Steps In Using SPSS In Computation

Step 1

Install the SPSS of any version such as 17.0, 18.0 and 21.0 etc on your PC or laptop using the SPSS CD or Downloaded temporarily from the internet.

Step 2

Get started with tour on the screen.

The command of the SPSS program depends on the type of installation. To get started from windows, just double click on the appropriate icon or select the program from a menu of options from window. The screen gives you a spread sheet with rows and columns. You can maximize if SPSS opens a small window instead of filling the whole screen. Sometimes, the screen may be partially obscured by another window asking "what do you want", with many options. If this happens just select "enter data", an click on the circle beside it

and click "Ok". On top of the screen is a program with the title (untitled – SPSS Data Editor) as well as minimize and restore button; the second line where you find words like "File", "Edit" etc is the menu bar, while the third line containing icons is the tool bar. If you click on any of the words in the menu bar, a dialog box pops up with options for carrying out special tasks.

Step 3

Enter your data into rows and columns and tell the program what the data depict by naming your variables using the Data Editor. The names of your variables will be used to specify the variable in your analysis and come out in the output.

Observe from figure 1 below that in the menu bar, we have File, Edit, View, Data, Transform, Analyze, Graphs, Utilities, Add-ons Window, Help. Each of these words provides a menu from which you choose what to do. you can use help to learn about what you can do with each option. the analysis menu is in most SPSS windows.

FIGURE 1: SPSS DATA EDITOR WINDOW

Step 4

Specify the type of analysis you want. This can be done by using the mouse to open the menus and dialogue boxes. Choose options from them for the syntax method you need to open the syntax Editor windows and then type command in SPSS programming language to specify the types of analysis desired.

Step 5

Examine and manipulate your output.

Once step 2 is complete, the output of the analysis will be displayed in a new window you may wish to (i) print results (ii) save output to computer, CD or data stick or other external saving device (iii) edit the output before saving or printing.

Saving the Files

You may wish to save the following files: (i) the data file (from data Editor) (ii) the output (from the output viewer) (iii) the SPSS program commands in the Syntax Editor if you are using the syntax method. The two data files differ in the format for which they are saved. It is advisable to give them names that can enable one to identify which data they represent. Always save it while the windows where the file located is active using the normal technique for saving . File extensions are obtained by using full stop sign (.) followed by three letters or words. For example Age.sav can represent an extension file containing ages of student.

the following are conventional ways of saving using different file extensions:

- * For the data file we use save extension. If data is in statistics scores we can write stat scores.sav for data file.
- * For syntax file add.sps to end of file. thus, we have statscore.sps
- * For output file the conventional method is adding.spo at the end of the

name. thus, we have statscore.spo as file name for the output.

Retrieving Files

Files are save so that they can be retrieved for viewing or use in future. Use the conventional method of clicking on file in the menu bar and selecting open from resulting menu. A list of files will be produced where you signify whether it is Data, Syntax or output file. Locate the file and double click it to open it.

Data

The table below shows the score of five males and five female students in a test:

Student	Sex	Scores
1	Male	65
2	Female	82
3	Female	63
4	Male	81
5	Female	48
6	Male	70
7	Male	52
8	Male	82
9	Female	91
10	Female	54

Obtain a descriptive statistics for this data.

Findings

Step 1: - Input the data as described earlier using one for male and two for female the data must be entered into the first three Columns in the Data Editor and label the variable as students' number, gender and score.

Step 2: - Click on Analyze on the menu bar; you will get options like descriptive statistics, compare means, Tables, Correlate, Regression, chi-square. Etc.

Step 3: - Click on descriptive statistics. You will get items like frequencies, descriptive, explore etc.

Step 4: - Select frequency; You will find that on the left side a box contains the names of your three variables i.e student, Gender and Score. On the right is another empty variable box. There is an arrow between the two boxes.

Step 5: - Double click on the variable name you want to get the frequency, it will automatically move to empty box. Select gender and score as our variable of interest.

Step 6: - Click Ok to run the analysis

Step 7: - Go back and select descriptive statistics at the bottom of the dialogue form. You will see the word statistics, charts and formats, click on statistics a new dialogue box containing other descriptive like central tendencies, dispersion etc.

Step 8: - Click on as many as you want. Such as chart option, independent t – test, one – way ANOVA etc.

Step 9: - Click Ok to run the analysis.

Example 1: Use the above data to carry out an independent sample t-test

Solution

Step 1: Click on Analyze on the menu bar

Step 2: Select compare means from the resulting menu

Step 3: Choose independent sample t-test

Step 4: You get a dialogue box with one box containing the three variables or another empty box on the right.

Step 5: Select your dependent variable which is the score

Step 6: Select your independent variable which is the gender

Step 7: Define your group which is one for males and two for females

Step 8: Click on continue to get back to dialogue box

Step 9: Click ok to run the data

Example 2

The below shows the marks obtained by 39 students in physics test and corresponding number of hours of study.

Hours of study X	4	9	10	14	4	7	12	22	1	20	15	8	3
Test mark Y	21	48	55	63	27	34	50	71	11	30	60	42	10
X	15	28	21	6	3	8	10	21	24	11	10	17	16
Y	51	85	54	25	12	35	40	61	65	43	54	71	64
X	26	27	9	10	15	20	29	30	14	17	23	25	24
Y	80	78	30	39	43	68	90	95	38	63	85	80	81

The test mark is the response (dependent) variable (Y) and the number of study hours is the predictor (independent) Variable (X).

To conduct a regression analyze from the menu-bar, select Regression and click o Linear. Move 'Marks' into the dependent variable list and move 'Study hour' into the dependent variable list. To obtain measures of location and dispersion, click on Statistic and select Descriptive. To obtain information about outlines and influential data points, click on save and select Unstandardized Predicted values, Leverage values, Cook's Distance and Standardized Deleted Residuals.

Descriptive Statistics

	Mean	Std. Deviation	N
Hour of Study (X)	15.08	8.158	39
Test Mark (Y)	52.62	22.924	39

The average test mark is 52.65 and the average number of study hour is 15.08. The standard deviations of the two variable vary considerably indicating that the dispersion of the mark is larger than the dispersion of the hours of study.

Model	Unstandardized coefficient		Standardized coefficients	T	Sig.
	B	Std. Error	Beta		
(constant)	14.230	3.342	.906	4.257	.000
Hours of study	2.546	.196		13.019	.000

There are two contending models to fit the data. The first is a one parameter model which is simply horizontal line whose Y-intercept is the average test mark. The second is a two-parameter model, which includes an intercept and a slope. The ANOVA test is used to establish which of the contender models fits the data best.

Since the p-value is less than the level of significance (0.05) H₀ is rejected and H₁ is accepted. This indicates that a two-parameter model fits the data significantly better than adequacy.

Coefficients

Model	Unstandardized coefficient		Standardized coefficients	T	Sig.
	B	Std. Error	Beta		
(constant)	14.230	3.342	.906	4.257	.000
Hours of study	2.546	.196		13.019	.000

$$Y_i = 2.54x_i + 14.23$$

This regression line can be used to make prediction. For example, the expected test mark for a student who did 14 hours of study before the test is $2.546(14) + 14.23$, which is approximately 50. However, the regression line cannot exceed 100. The p-value indicates whether the parameter estimates

are significantly different from zero. In this example, both p-values are less than level of sig. (0.05) indicating that both parameters are significantly different from zero.

Model Summary (Correlation Coefficient)

Model	R	R square	Adjusted R square	Std. error of the estimate
	.906	.821	.816	9.834

The correlation R measures the relationship between the observed test mark and the number of hours of study. The correlation ($R = 0.96$) between these two variables is positive and significantly different from 0. This indicates that there is a strong positive relationship between the two variables, which is not attributed to chance. The coefficient of determination R^2 is a measure of the goodness of fit and measures the percentage variability explained by the two-parameter regression model. This coefficient is the ratio of the regression and sum of squares SS_{Reg} and total SS_{Total} which are both available in the ANOVA table.

$R^2 = 0.821$ indicates that the two-parameter model explain 82.1% of the variability of each data. This implies that knowing the number of hours of study explains 82.1% of the variability of the test mark

Interpretation of Result

It is essential that one should be able to interpret results from output of statistical data processed by the computers. Most of the outputs bring out frequency counts and other descriptive statistics some of which are mean and standard deviation, regression coefficients, standard errors and coefficient of determination. The observed significant levels are also brought out especially when testing hypotheses for 2 – tailed test the value double that of 1 – tailed

test. One should be able to consult standard statistical test book for the interpretation. In test of hypothesis, the p – value which is the observed level of significance comes out in the output. The rule to use is that if the p – value is less than the level of significance, the null hypothesis can be rejected. For simple linear regression, the regression co-efficient is an indication of the amount of increase in the dependent variable brought about by one unit increase in the independent variable. The beta weights on the multiple regression gives indication of contribution of each variable to the model. In Correlation Coefficient, the interpretation can be (-1.0 to -0.7) strong negative association, (-0.7 to -0.3) weak negative association, (-0.3 to +0.3) little or no association, (+0.3 to +0.7) weak positive association, (+.7 to +1.0), strong positive association. The co-efficient of determination gives the percentage of variation in the dependent variable that can be accounted for by variation in the independent variable.

Conclusion

It is essential that effort should be made to be conversant with these software packages. One can start with free online trial versions and follow the steps stipulated for its usage. Many of the packages come with easy and efficient step by step procedure for data analysis. One should be able to interpret and assist others, as educationalist, mathematicians and statisticians in interpreting processed statistical data to enhance better decision making.

Recommendations

It is pertinent that the choice of appropriate statistics to apply for analyzing any research data depends on the nature of data which itself depends on the type of design of the study. The more complicated the design is, the more sophisticated the appropriate statistics will be. It is strongly

suggested that any survey research should generally rely on descriptive statistics while experimental and correlational researches demand inferential statistics. With the aid of computer and statistical software packages, I consider manual computation should become almost unnecessary. However, serious minded educational researchers should be able to choose the correct statistics to apply for the purpose of making the outcome of their studies meaningful to readers of their reports particularly other researchers. What constitutes good statistics is one that gives the best interpretation which the research evidence permits.

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